

EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN AND UNITED KINGDOM

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Abstract. Education is the milestone of the each nation and society as without it we can not imagine how the life we are living would like be. In this article, the researchers will concentrate on the importance of education and discuss about the differences and similarities between Uzbek and English education systems.

Key words: education, system, school, university, primary school, nursery education, curriculum.

From the early history, human beings have acquired and mastered more and more things for surviving and making his life better: first, we learnt how to pick up berries, created wood -made objects to kill animals for food, then we learnt how to make fire and the number of innovations continued on after the development of the human intellect. All of those actions happened throughout the history which made humans to become more curious about acquiring new knowledge and made them try to make their life more better. Thus, education took a leading role step by step and people started to grow.

Every country and nation cannot imagine their future without education, as there is no development, no advancement where education is not paid much attention. First of all, let's make clear what is education? Education is the most important thing in our life. Every country has their methods and ways to teach children. Everything we learn in life is also education. It also means helping people to learn how to do things and support them to think about what they learn. It is also important for educators to teach ways to find and use information. Education need research to find out how to make it better. And also education makes a difference you take proper choice in life. We will explain and give some

information about differences and similarities of education system in United Kingdom and Uzbekistan. Education system in Uzbekistan is divided into several steps. They are: nursery, primary, secondary, higher, undergraduate, postgraduate. For example, the nursery stage begins from 2 to 5. In Uzbekistan 11 years of education are compulsory and free. The nursery schools teach the basics to kids, giving them a strong foundation for the elementary years. This includes academic concepts of literacy and math, such as counting and letter recognition and developing .Primary school begin at the age of 6. They teach to 10 age. The following 5 years are spent at general secondary school from ages 10 to 15. And the pupils have ability to apply the technical vocational schools. It help them to enter the university, or somebody has a certificate or diplom which was given by vocational schools, they easily get a job without entering the university . There is a higher education. When the pupil apply for the document to the university ,after graduating school. He or she has a lot of opportunities to read well. Because our university education system is very well. Today students have wide opportunities. Also, there is a undergraduate stage.

An undergraduate is a collage or university student who is not a graduate student. After high school, you can become an undergraduate. Undergraduates are students if universities and colleges, they have graduated from high school and have been accepted to collage, but they have not graduate yet. A postgraduate is a stage that, the students finish the university and they have already advanced level knowledge. The Uzbekistan education system is these. If we comes to United Kingdom's teaching ways.UK primary school education begins in the UK at the age 5 and continues untill age 11. It is differ from Uzbekistan's system. And they divided primary schools into 2 groups . The infant age range is from age 5 to 7. The junior age range is from age 7 to 11. The next stage is secondary school. 7 or 8 aged children are the first 2 years of secondary school education in the UK. In some independent schools they are contained the Junior school, but others are part of the Senior. School. The following stage is further education or vocational

courses. In this stage, students enter the collages. All collages can prepare students to enter the universities or other countries universities. The British school system also extends to BTEC courses which are designed for students who would like to develop practiced knowledge and skills in a specific subject (Business, Phycology, Engineering, Sport, Art, Design)and find traditional exams challenging. And there are also undergraduate study. In the UK, a British bachelor's degree normally takes 3 years to finish and awarded at honors level. Examples of first degrees are: BA(Bachelor's of Art), Beng (Bachelor's of Engineering),and BSC(Bachelor's of Science). Afterwards, postgraduate study. Postgraduate courses in the UK education are very intensive. This means that the courses much shorter than other countries. Master's degree usually takes 12 months. Master's of Business Administration is a high Masters course which takes 2 years. A PhD degree in the UK can take 2 and 7 years.

As you can see, both United Kingdom and Uzbekistan have some differences and similarities on their education system. For example, in UK ,the pre-school begins at the age of 2 -3. However, in Uzbekistan ,the preschool training begins 3-6 years old. Also, UK's pupils study from Monday to Friday. When it comes to Uzbekistan, pupils study from Monday to Sunday. In UK, lessons begin at 08:00 or 09:00 am,but in Uzbekistan lessons usually start 08:00 am. All in all, there are big differences between these two countries education system.

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